

INFLUENCE OF THE SPOT SIZE IN TRANSIENT GRATING SPECTROSCOPY

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Abstract

The influence of spot size on the quality of the time- and frequency-domain results of transient grating spectroscopy (TGS) was investigated. The experiment was performed on a single-crystalline sample of Ni with a highly symmetrical cut (110). Sharpening of the frequency peaks of the SAW was observed for larger spot sizes. However, the best obtainable sharpness of the frequency peaks strongly depends on the crystallographic direction of the propagating SAW. Ultra-transient effects observable in UTGS measurements depended strongly on the power density of the pump laser.

Keywords: *transient grating spectroscopy, elastic anisotropy, surface acoustic waves, single-crystals*

1. Introduction

Transient grating spectroscopy (TGS) is a non-destructive and contactless opto-acoustic technique used to characterize the elastic and thermal properties of materials [1], [2], [3]. In a reflective geometry used for opaque solids, TGS was used to determine the elastic properties of single-crystalline [3], [4], thin-film characterization [5], [6], [7], martensitic transformation [8], irradiation effects [9], [10], [11], thermal diffusivity [12], [13], and polycrystalline samples [14], [15]. Recently, the existence of ultra-transient features was described as the ultra-transient grating spectroscopy (UTGS) approach [16], leading to experimental reconstruction of elastodynamic frequency-domain Green's function of the surface acoustic response [17].

TGS uses two pulsed laser beams interfering on the sample surface, which results in the spatially harmonic thermo-elastic excitation, where each of the excitation fringes acts as a thermo-elastic line-like source. This leads to a strong constraint on the spatial characteristics of the surface thermo-acoustic source, forming dynamic surface-displacement grating on which the probe beams diffract. The probe laser is continuous, and the optical geometry ensures recombination of the probe beams in a heterodyne detection setup [1]. The relative phase shift of the probe beams (the heterodyne phase) then influences the information obtained. The 'phase-grating' mode with the heterodyne phase

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Figure 1: a) top-view schematic of the simplified optical setup of the TGS method. b) Interference pattern with a fixed 2:1 pump-to-probe size ratio. Cylindrical lens is used to create a highly-elliptical spot for both pump and probe.

$\theta_{\text{het}} = (\pm\pi/2)$ allows us to measure thermal and elastic properties simultaneously [2], [13], [18].

Most analytic treatments assume an infinite, uniform grating, [18], [19], [20] but real experiments use finite, typically Gaussian, pump and probe beams. Despite routine consideration of grating period and beam overlap in experimental design, the influence of finite spot sizes—through effects such as beam diffraction, Gaussian envelope truncation, spatial averaging of dynamics, and non-uniform excitation densities—has been the subject of comparatively few systematic studies. Finite beam diameters modify the ideal sinusoidal excitation profile and reduce the effective intensity of the grating at the edges.

This paper examines how the sizes of pump and probe spots—with a fixed 2:1 size ratio, but varying absolute size—influence the quality of the TGS signal in the time- and frequency-domains for a single-crystalline sample with elastic anisotropy.

2. Methods - Transient Grating Spectroscopy

Transient grating spectroscopy in reflective geometry, illustrated in Fig. 1, uses a transmission phase mask for a diffraction of pump and probe lasers and projecting ± 1 diffraction order beams on the sample surface using the 4F imaging system. Projected pump beams interfere on the sample surface, creating a spatially harmonic excitation pattern. The harmonic pattern leads to the formation of thermal and acoustic transient gratings, on which the probe beams are diffracted.

A fixed 2:1 pump-to-probe beam diameter ratio is maintained throughout the discussed measurements. A cylindrical lens is used to create a highly-elliptical spot for both lasers to have higher energy density within the pattern while maintaining larger number of wavelengths. The optical setup is in the Littrow configuration, where each probe beam diffracts in the reflection direction of the other, enabling interferometric ('heterodyne') detection. Detection is carried out in the 'phase-grating' mode (with the heterodyne phase $\theta_{\text{het}} = (\pm\pi/2)$), which maximizes sensitivity to out-of-plane displacement.

The measurement setup was similar to that used in the previous work of the authors [3]. The pump laser was a Nd:YAG laser (1064 nm, 0.54 ns, 200 μJ , 1 kHz). The probe beams were from the continuous-wave laser at 532 nm (120 mW) with mean power on detector around 15 mW for all measurements. The signal-to-noise ratio and sensitivity are increased by measuring the intensity using Si photodiodes with a 60 dB amplifier. The differential setup further enhances the signal quality by removing phase-insensitive influences [18], [21].

The signal was recorded by WaveRunner 640Zi oscilloscope (4 GHz bandwidth, vertical resolution of 8 bits, sampling rate 5 GS/s) and averaged 50 thousand times in the time-domain for further reduction of noise. The Fourier analysis then reveals the dominant SAW frequencies, from which the SAW velocities were obtained using $v = f\lambda$, where λ is the excitation grating period.

The fringe spacing, and thus the acoustic wavelength λ , is determined by the period d_{PM} of the phase mask and the magnification M of the 4F imaging system. For normal incidence on the phase mask, the diffraction condition $\sin(\theta/2) = \lambda_{\text{opt}}/d_{PM}$ causes the optical wavelength to cancel, giving:

$$\lambda = \frac{d_{PM}}{2M}, \quad (1)$$

where θ is the angle between the two excitation beams [22]. When holding the normal incidence (disregarding the phase-mask tilting), the acoustic wavelength can therefore be changed by swapping the phase mask (changing d_{PM}) or by changing the lenses in the 4F imaging system (changing M)—which, however, affects the pattern size at the sample.

3. Results and Discussion

The sample used in this study was a nickel single-crystal with cubic symmetry and Zener anisotropy ratio $Z = 2.6$. The high-symmetry cut, (110) in Miller indices, was chosen as this allows comparison of highly-symmetrical directions, like [100], with more arbitrary direction, in the (110) plane.

Three measurement configurations were performed, each combining a different phase mask period d_{PM} and 4F imaging system magnification M such that the acoustic wavelength λ remained $\approx 10 \mu\text{m}$ in all cases, while the effective pump spot size varied from

Table 1: Phase mask used in the measurement with a corresponding focal length ratio used in the 4F imaging system. The effective pump spot size was determined from the oscillation time of Ni(110)[100].

Phase mask (μm)	f1:f2	Pump (μm)
20	2:1	≈ 450
10	1:1	≈ 900
5	1:2	≈ 1800

450 μm to 1800 μm (Table 1). The power of the probe beams was constant for all measurements. For the largest and middle spot sizes, the pump beam average power was kept the same; for the smallest spot, it was reduced to avoid surface ablation.

3.1. Time-domain signal and effective spot size

The comparison of the obtained time-domain signals in the chosen crystallographic direction is shown in Fig. 2. We can observe that for the angle 0° —corresponding to [100] direction—the time of the oscillations scales linearly with a spot size. This is expected as in such principal direction on a single-crystalline sample, the SAW oscillation lifetime corresponds directly to the pattern size (or more precisely, to the number of wavelengths within it) as it avoids any influences of elastic anisotropy [3]. Thus, the effective pump spot size noted in Table 1 was determined from the oscillation time in this direction.

However, for the angle 30° , the SAW lifetime is notably shorter, with much lower correlation to the spot size—there is only a small increase in oscillation time between the smallest and middle size spots and no difference between the biggest and middle size spots. This is likely due to the elastic anisotropy, which causes the SAW to be of more complex polarization (with lower out-of-plane component), and introduces energy steering (meaning that SAWs generated farther from the probing spot can miss it and avoid being detected). The optimal spot size for the longest oscillation time therefore depends on the crystallographic directions.

3.2. Angular-resolved velocity maps

For all 4F system configurations—and thus different pattern sizes—the full angular dispersion was measured in the range of 90° , with a step of 1° . Comparison of the resulting angular-resolved velocity maps in Fig. 3 (showing frequency spectra recalculated to velocity as $v = f\lambda$) shows sharpening of the SAW peaks near principal directions—[001] at 0° , [1 $\bar{1}$ 1] near 60° , and [0 $\bar{1}$ 1] at 90° —for larger spot sizes, correlating with longer oscillations in the time-domain. However, for most directions there is only small improvement in the SAW peak prominence between the smallest and middle spot sizes and nearly no change between the biggest and middle spot sizes. Again, this is correlated with what we observe for the angle 30° in the time-domain in Fig. 2.

Figure 2: Comparison of the TGS time-domain signals in Ni(110)[100] as angle 0° (a, b and c) and angle 30° (d, e and f). Measured signals in solid blue and numerical difference of measured signals in solid orange to better show differences in acoustic oscillations. Top row represent smallest spot size, middle row the middle size, and bottom row largest spot size described in Table 1.

Figure 3 d) shows a calculated elastodynamic surface frequency-domain Green’s function [17], which is the response to a spatially harmonic source, and thus represents the idealized infinite-spot limit. The correspondence to the measured signals shows that the ultra-transient features—finer features in the spectra connected to bulk waves, which are observed only in a short time after the excitation [16]—are clearly better resolved for the middle spot size than for the smallest one. However, their resolution does not improve for the biggest spot size, which is consistent with the fact that the middle and the biggest spots had the same total pump power, leading to different power densities. This suggests that the quality of these features is governed by the pump power density within the pattern rather than simply by the pattern size.

4. Conclusion

In this work, we present the results of spot-size modifications on the resulting data quality of the TGS measurement. For principal crystallographic directions, increased spot size produces longer SAW oscillation lifetimes and correspondingly sharper peaks in the frequency domain. However, the improvement depends on the crystallographic direction — and little to no influence of spot size can be found in directions where the generalized surface wave has a low out-of-plane displacement component, or where its energy steers away from the k -vector direction given by the pattern (and the counter-propagating waves do not meet in the detection spot). The strength of ultra-transient features depends on the power density within the excitation pattern. Their prominence above noise, while expected to improve with larger pattern size, requires

further study with varying pump pattern parameters and pump-to-probe spot size ratios.

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Figure 3: Comparison of experimental angular-resolved velocity maps with a computed frequency-domain Green's function response to a spatially harmonic source, (a,b,c) showing the smallest, middle, and largest spot size, respectively; (d) shows the calculated frequency-domain elastodynamic Green's function. All maps are normalized to the highest peak and the colorbar shows the logarithmic amplitude of the frequency spectra, $\log_{10}(A)$ (a.u.) — note how the peak prominence given by the relative coloring differs (in logarithmic scale).

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